

1 **Novel short-term national strategies to promote the use of**
2 **renewable hydrogen in road transport: a life cycle assessment**
3 **of passenger car fleets partially fuelled with hydrogen**

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11 **Abstract**

12 This work presents an energy analysis combined with a comparative environmental life
13 cycle assessment (LCA) of eight different passenger car fleets that use renewable
14 hydrogen and a conventional fuel (natural gas or gasoline) under the same total energy
15 input and the same hydrogen-to-mixture energy ratio. The fleets under comparison
16 involve vehicles that use the two fuels separately or in a mixture. Using Italy as an
17 illustrative country, this research work aims to help policy-makers implement well-
18 supported strategies to promote the use of hydrogen in road transport in the short term.
19 The proposed strategies achieve a carbon footprint reduction between 7% and 35% with
20 respect to their conventional fleet benchmark. Within the current context, the results
21 suggest the energy and environmental suitability of using hydrogen blends as short-term
22 solutions, involving vehicles that require minor modifications with respect to current
23 compressed natural gas vehicles and gasoline vehicles, while paving the way for pure
24 hydrogen mobility.

25

26 **Keywords:** hydrogen, natural gas, sustainable mobility, road transport, national energy
27 and climate plan, life cycle assessment

28 **1. Introduction**

29 *1.1. Contextualisation of the study*

30 Awareness of responsibility for anthropogenic climate change has grown
31 worldwide, and environmental issues are gaining centrality in the public debate. Policy
32 and scientific actors worldwide recognise, with ever greater strength, the urgency for
33 actions to avoid a climate catastrophe in the years to come. In 2015, near 200 countries
34 negotiated the Paris agreement, the first universal and legally binding covenant on the
35 global climate, aiming to limit global warming to well below +2 °C compared to the pre-
36 industrial era (UNFCCC, 2015). Furthermore, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate
37 Change (2018) underlines the urgency to act drastically by 2030 to limit global warming
38 below +1.5 °C. The Glasgow Climate Pact, which came out of the 26th United Nations
39 Climate Change conference (2021), confirms the need to pursue efforts to maintain global
40 warming below the 1.5 °C increase. In this context, Europe has set a carbon-neutrality
41 target by 2050 (European Commission, 2019), with more and more ambitious
42 intermediate goals for 2030, in a process of constant upward revision.

43 The main cause of these environmental issues lies in the massive use of fossil fuels
44 for energy purposes. In 2018, the world primary energy demand amounted to 14,282
45 million tonnes of oil equivalent (Mtoe), of which 81% was met by fossil fuels (IEA,
46 2020). The transport sector is particularly energy demanding and relies almost entirely on
47 fossil fuels, thus releasing a considerable amount of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. In
48 Europe, the transport sector represents above 30% of energy consumption in final uses

49 (287 Mtoe in 2018) (Eurostat, 2020) and is annually responsible for more than 1 Gt of
50 equivalent CO₂ (CO₂ eq), corresponding to around 25% of the total European GHG
51 emissions (EEA, 2019, 2018a). Road transport, for both freight and passengers, is by far
52 the dominant transport mode, constituting more than 70% of the sectoral energy
53 consumption and emissions (EEA, 2019, 2018a, 2018b; Eurostat, 2020). The greatest
54 energy consumption is associated with passenger transport, in which the predominant
55 vehicle category is constituted by light-duty vehicles and passenger cars (EIA, 2019),
56 which in Europe make up 83% of inland passenger transport (Eurostat, 2020).

57 Hence, the implementation of decarbonisation solutions for passenger cars is
58 pivotal. In this sense, hydrogen arises as a promising solution (Bicer and Dincer, 2018;
59 IEA, 2019) since its use phase does not involve direct carbon emissions; nevertheless, in
60 compliance with environmental criteria, its production should rely on renewable sources
61 (Dincer, 2012). In recent years, the European Union (EU) has paved the way to the energy
62 transition (i) with the new renewable energy directive 2018/2001 (RED-II) (European
63 Union, 2018), (ii) by requiring that member states draw up national energy and climate
64 plans (NECPs) to meet EU targets by 2030 (European Commission, 2018), and (iii) by
65 assigning a strategic role to hydrogen produced from renewables. The latter is evinced by
66 the European strategy for hydrogen (European Commission, 2020) and the development
67 of various hydrogen national strategies (BMW_i, 2020; MiSE, 2020; MITERD, 2020),
68 some of which are still under definition.

69 The RED-II and NECPs define, for the different countries, the target trajectories
70 and the share of renewable energy to be achieved in the various energy uses, including
71 transport. Many European countries such as Italy plan to fill a relatively small part of this

72 renewable quota through the introduction of renewable hydrogen in transport, mainly by
73 introducing fuel cell electric vehicles (FCEV) in their fleets (MiSE, 2020, 2019;
74 MITERD, 2020). Although this represents a starting point for the development of a
75 hydrogen economy relevant to the transport sector, a large-scale deployment of FCEVs
76 seems to be still a long way off. Core barriers involve (i) the need to start massive
77 production of renewable hydrogen from scratch and, therefore, a limited green hydrogen
78 availability in the short term; (ii) the lack of a hydrogen distribution grid/infrastructure
79 and, in particular, refuelling points; and (iii) current limitations of a technical, economic
80 or social nature at the vehicle level. Therefore, innovative strategies that circumvent these
81 barriers while favouring the use of hydrogen in the short term should be explored.

82 *1.2. Motivation and novelty*

83 On a national scale, in the short term, passenger car fleets would be fuelled only
84 partially with hydrogen, as only relatively small amounts of renewable hydrogen would
85 be available. On the other hand, it should be noted that the use of hydrogen in pure form
86 is not the only option and several studies have shown the possibility to inject it into the
87 natural gas (NG) network to a certain extent (Altfeld and Pinchbeck, 2013; European
88 Commission, 2009; IEA, 2019; Kippers et al., 2011) or use it in mixture, for vehicular
89 applications, with other fuels such as NG (Çeper, 2012; Genovese et al., 2011; Yan et al.,
90 2017), gasoline (Akif Ceviz et al., 2012; Niu et al., 2016; Yu et al., 2017) or diesel (Vavra
91 et al., 2019). It is therefore conceivable to propose different options of passenger car fleets
92 that use both hydrogen and traditional fuels in diverse ways. However, to ensure an
93 effective action, it is necessary to assess and compare the alternatives in terms of their
94 energy and environmental performance. In order to conduct a comprehensive and sound

95 comparison of the performance of different fleets involving hydrogen, a life-cycle
96 approach is required. For this purpose, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a consolidated
97 methodology, as it allows analysts to compare different systems performing the same
98 function and identify environmental hotspots (ISO, 2006a, 2006b).

99 In the automotive sector, well-to-wheels (WTW) analyses are most frequently
100 conducted, including their subsets known as well-to-tank (WTT) and tank-to-wheels
101 (TTW) depending on the definition of the system boundaries (Orsi et al., 2016; Torchio
102 and Santarelli, 2010; Yazdanie et al., 2014). However, WTW analyses typically consider
103 only some (fuel-related) life-cycle stages (i.e., fuel production, distribution up to the
104 vehicle tank, and fuel use), while a vehicle LCA typically considers the WTW stages as
105 well as the manufacturing, maintenance and end-of-life stages of the vehicle itself,
106 thereby extending the system's boundaries (JEC, 2014; Ricardo E&E, 2020).

107 In a previous study, Candelaresi et al. (2021a) investigated the life-cycle
108 environmental performance of different passenger car options fuelled with pure hydrogen
109 or hydrogen blends (H₂-NG and H₂-gasoline), taking into account the life-cycle stages of
110 vehicle production and maintenance in addition to the fuel-related ones. Renewable
111 hydrogen produced through wind power electrolysis (WPE) was considered in the study.
112 This previous work showed that: (i) vehicles fuelled with pure hydrogen are excellent
113 decarbonisation solutions; (ii) for pure renewable hydrogen vehicles, according to current
114 technology levels, vehicle infrastructure is the main source of environmental burdens;
115 and (iii) vehicles with internal combustion engine (ICE) that use hydrogen mixed with
116 fossil fuels (gasoline and NG) present an improved life-cycle environmental performance

117 compared to traditional vehicles, arising as suitable short-term options temporarily
118 circumventing major hydrogen storage and distribution issues.

119 Considering this background and the limited availability of hydrogen on a national
120 scale, this work aims to give insight into environmentally-preferred passenger car fleets
121 partially fuelled with hydrogen. Ultimately, the goal of this study is to provide policy
122 actors with well-supported information in order to accelerate the resource-efficient
123 implementation of renewable hydrogen in road transport. The main novelty lies in the
124 proposal of innovative national strategies to promote the use of hydrogen in road
125 passenger transport in the short term. The suitability of the proposals is evaluated by
126 performing a comparative LCA of passenger car fleets that use hydrogen and traditional
127 fuels either separately (in different vehicles) or in a mixture (in the same vehicle). In order
128 to enable a fair comparison, fleet alternatives are defined under the same energy input. In
129 addition, within the framework of the study, life-cycle inventories for two new vehicle
130 types not available in the literature (hybrid electric vehicles, HEV, that burn hydrogen
131 blends in their ICE) are developed.

132 **2. Material and methods**

133 This study addresses the definition and identification of passenger car fleets
134 partially fuelled with hydrogen that could be both energy and environmentally convenient
135 in the short term, under the constraint of a limited fixed amount of hydrogen available on
136 a national scale. While Italy was taken as a reference country for some assumptions
137 (Section 2.2), the proposed methodological approach could be applied to a large number
138 of countries in a similar situation. Likewise, while –in accordance with previous work
139 (Candelaresi et al., 2021a)– hydrogen from WPE was considered in this study, the

140 analysis could be extended to other renewable hydrogen options with low environmental
141 impacts. Nine types of vehicles were considered, which in turn were combined in eight
142 different fleets. Four fleets are fuelled by hydrogen and NG, whereas the remaining ones
143 by hydrogen and gasoline, with an energy equivalent amount. The fleets under analysis
144 can use the two fuels separately or as a mixture inside the same vehicle. Other options
145 such as diesel internal combustion engine vehicles or battery electric vehicles are out of
146 the scope of this study. Furthermore, this study should be understood within the expected
147 context of coexistence of complementary solutions for sustainable mobility such as
148 hydrogen vehicles and battery electric vehicles (Staffell et al., 2019; Valente et al., 2021).

149 *2.1. Technical background*

150 Regarding blends, the Italian transmission system operator Snam has already
151 experimented with the injection of hydrogen into some sections of its NG grids at
152 different volumetric percentages, demonstrating that it is possible to transport H₂ up to
153 10%_{vol} blended with NG in the existing infrastructure (SNAM, 2020). In fact, other
154 studies have demonstrated the technical feasibility of blending hydrogen in the NG grid
155 in higher amounts (IEA, 2019; Melaina et al., 2013), with minor technical concerns when
156 the hydrogen content is less than 20%_{vol} (European Commission, 2009; Kippers et al.,
157 2011; Kouchachvili and Entchev, 2018).

158 Regarding final uses, the Italian companies Fiat and Iveco have already
159 experimented with the use of H₂-NG mixtures in ICEs, demonstrating the possibility of
160 using mixtures with 20%_{vol} or even up to 30%_{vol} of H₂ (Il Sole 24 Ore, 2012; IVECO,
161 2010a, 2010b; NGV Journal, 2011). Moreover, there are several studies in the scientific
162 literature dealing with H₂-NG or H₂-gasoline mixtures, at different proportions, to fuel

163 ICES (Anstrom and Collier, 2016; Genovese and Villante, 2013; Pana et al., 2007; Shi et
164 al., 2017). Generally, the results show that –after optimising the engine parameters– the
165 addition of hydrogen improves the combustion characteristics, increasing engine
166 efficiency and reducing fuel consumption and emissions (Luo et al., 2020).

167 Figure 1 shows the vehicles considered in the present study for the definition of
168 fleets. Detailed information of the single vehicles is given in previous studies
169 (Candelaresi et al., 2021a; Valente et al., 2020). As regards pure hydrogen-fuelled
170 solutions, only FCEVs were considered.

171 On the other hand, vehicles equipped with ICE powertrain include: compressed
172 natural gas (CNG) vehicle, gasoline vehicle, hythane vehicle, and dual-fuel hydrogen-
173 gasoline vehicle. Hythane[®] is a commercial name for a gaseous mixture of 20%_{vol} H₂ and
174 80%_{vol} NG; for a fair comparison, the hydrogen-gasoline mixture was considered with an
175 energy ratio of the mixture equal to that of hythane (i.e., H₂ provides 7.3% of the mixture
176 energy). HEVs of the full-hybrid, series/parallel type were also considered. These
177 comprehend HEVs fuelled with compressed natural gas (HEV CNG) or gasoline (HEV
178 Gasoline). In addition, for the first time, two novel HEVs were considered in the present
179 study: an HEV fuelled with hythane (HEV Hythane), and an HEV fuelled with a
180 hydrogen-gasoline mixture (HEV H₂-Gasoline).

181 An average European passenger car with a rated vehicle power of 80 kW was
182 considered as reference, taking into account the different powertrain technologies to
183 model each of the different vehicle options. The reference car is a sedan type, 5-door,
184 belonging to segment C (small family cars/compact cars). Further details on the bill of
185 materials for car manufacturing and use can be found in Candelaresi et al. (2021a).

189 By using the above-mentioned vehicle options, the fleets subject to comparison
190 were defined as follows: fleet F1 involving CNG vehicles and FCEVs; F2 involving
191 Hythane; F3 with HEV CNG and FCEVs; F4 with HEV Hythane; F5 with Gasoline
192 vehicles and FCEVs; F6 with H₂-Gasoline vehicles; F7 with HEV Gasoline and FCEVs;
193 and F8 with HEV H₂-Gasoline. Hence, fleets from F1 to F4 are fuelled by NG and
194 hydrogen, while fleets from F5 to F8 by gasoline and hydrogen. The number of vehicles
195 in each fleet is not defined here because it derives from the energy analysis as an
196 intermediate result (Section 3.1).

197 *2.2. Energy analysis and national contextualisation*

198 In order to maximise the penetration of hydrogen-related vehicles in national
199 fleets, it is necessary to promote fleets that use the available fuels with high efficiency.
200 The aim of this energy analysis is to explore, given a fixed amount of fuel, which fleets
201 can travel higher distances. In countries with a high number of passenger cars, even the
202 achievement of a small hydrogen penetration (e.g., 1% of the national fleet) could be a
203 challenging short-term target. For instance, Italy is the second country in the European
204 Union with the largest number of passenger cars, 646 per thousand inhabitants (Eurostat,
205 2020); according to the Italian Automobile Club (ACI, 2021), there were 39,717,874 cars
206 in circulation on the Italian roads in 2020. Some constraints were set to carry out the
207 energy analysis, mainly regarding the quantity of the two fuels available in each fleet in
208 a year, fuel consumption and annual driving performance of each vehicle. The driving
209 performance, namely the average distance travelled by one vehicle in a year, was assumed
210 to be 15,000 km.

211 For comparative purposes, each fleet was fed with the same amount of total energy
212 input, supplied in the form of two fuels. In particular, the amount of hydrogen available
213 was set the same for all fleets, while the remaining part of the energy is supplied with
214 CNG or gasoline. The amount of available hydrogen was assumed on the basis of NECPs
215 and national hydrogen strategies, while the analysis is scalable to different hydrogen
216 amounts. The amount of fossil fuel was subsequently calculated by considering an energy
217 share of H₂ and fossil fuel of 7.3% and 92.7% of the available energy, respectively. This
218 is the energy share fixed by hythane, and it was assumed to be the same in every case in
219 order to put all fleets under the same conditions.

220 Regarding the hydrogen amount, the RED-II and the Italian NECP set the
221 objectives to be achieved for Italy as a share of renewable energy sources in the final
222 gross energy consumption of transport (RES-T) at 22% by 2030 and 14.4% by 2025
223 (European Union, 2018; MiSE, 2019). However, as part of the “Fit for 55” package
224 proposed in July 2021 by the European Commission (2021), the RED-II is undergoing a
225 review process and these objectives could become more ambitious in the coming years.
226 According to the NECP (MiSE, 2019), the preliminary guidelines for the Italian national
227 hydrogen strategy (MiSE, 2020) and the more recent national recovery and resilience plan
228 (NRRP) (Italian Council of Ministers, 2021), Italy plans to reach one percentage point of
229 the RES-T target by 2030 through the use of green hydrogen. The NECP also suggests
230 that a part of this hydrogen might be blended in the NG network or converted into
231 renewable synthetic methane (0.8 percentage points of the RES-T target) while the
232 remaining hydrogen might be used “as is” (i.e., in pure form) for direct use in cars, buses

233 and trains (0.2 percentage points). As a 1% hydrogen-related target is set for 2030, a 0.5%
234 short-term target was assumed for 2025.

235 According to the statistics of the Italian energy services operator (GSE), the
236 national energy consumption in the transport sector amounted to 39,830 ktoe in 2019,
237 with 83.2% of this value coming from road transport (GSE, 2021). The energy
238 consumption foreseen by the NECP and the GSE report for the Italian transport in 2025
239 is 28,851 ktoe, which corresponds to the denominator considered for the calculation of
240 the targets according to the RED-II procedure. Taking into account the hydrogen-specific
241 0.5% target for 2025 and the calculation procedure shown in Figure 2, a hydrogen
242 availability above 5 kt was estimated for Italian passenger cars in 2025. This is aligned
243 with the national goals and the short-term perspective of the study, considering the need
244 to start massive production of renewable hydrogen from scratch.

245 According to the previously defined energy ratio (7.3%), the amounts of CNG
246 (168 kt) or gasoline (183.8 kt) available for each fleet in 2025, as well as the total energy
247 (8.65 PJ), were derived. This means that, in energy terms for the year 2025, each fleet
248 uses 8.65 PJ of energy: 0.63 PJ of hydrogen and 8.02 PJ of fossil fuel (NG or gasoline).

249 Finally, operational parameters for each vehicle, namely fuel consumption and
250 tailpipe emissions, were based on Candelaresi et al. (2021a), where data from
251 manufacturer declarations and technical datasheets are used along with scientific
252 literature and databases such as GREET and Ecoscore (Timmermans et al., 2006; Vrije
253 Universiteit Brussel, 2006).

254

255 **Figure 2:** Calculation procedure for the target use of hydrogen in Italian passenger cars
 256 in 2025.

257 Table 1 presents fuel economy (i.e., the reciprocal of fuel consumption), energy
 258 consumption and tailpipe emissions for each of the nine vehicles involved in fleets
 259 composition. For the sake of completeness, water emissions were included (as they could

260 be relevant for other purposes, including the implementation of future progress in
 261 characterisation factors for water emissions) even though they do not currently affect the
 262 LCA results of this study. Values for fuel consumption refer to NEDC (New European
 263 Driving Cycle) under a combined cycle (urban/extra-urban route). The main
 264 considerations behind the energy analysis of fleets are summarised in Figure 3.

265 **Table 1:** Fuel economy and tailpipe emissions for the vehicles involved in fleets composition based on
 266 (Candelaresi et al., 2021a).

Vehicle	Fuel economy [km/kg]	Energy consumption ^a [MJ/km]	CO ₂ [g/km]	CO [mg/km]	HC ^b [mg/km]	NO _x [mg/km]	H ₂ O ^c [g/km]
FCEV	131.58	0.912	-	-	-	-	67.9
CNG	29.240	1.631	94	48.25	29.4	16.8	76.8
HEV CNG	44.303	1.077	66.888	32.33	20.1	4.9	50.7
Hythane	34.382	1.451	75.670	27.79	19.4	26.9	71.3
HEV Hythane	52.094	0.958	53.845	18.62	13.3	7.9	47.0
Gasoline	26.667	1.635	105.4	292.54	41.2	20.5	53.2
HEV Gasoline	40.404	1.079	75	196	28.2	6.0	35.1
H₂-Gasoline	31.352	1.459	87.146	102.27	25.8	33.7	52.0
HEV H₂-Gasoline	47.503	0.963	62.011	68.52	17.6	9.9	34.3

^a Lower heating values of the fuels involved: 120 MJ/kg for hydrogen; 47.7 MJ/kg for CNG; 43.6 MJ/kg for gasoline; 49.9 MJ/kg for hythane; and 45.7 MJ/kg for H₂-Gasoline.

^b HC: unburned hydrocarbons.

^c Stoichiometric values; gasoline was considered as iso-octane.

267

268 Altogether, Table 1 and Figures 2 and 3 present the key assumptions made for the
 269 study at the level of both national hydrogen availability (Figure 2) and technical features
 270 of vehicles (Table 1) and fleets (Figure 3).

Total energy input for each fleet: 8.65 PJ/year
 Each fleet is fuelled with:

271

272 **Figure 3:** Main assumptions for the energy analysis of fleets.

273 *2.3. LCA framework*

274 In order to investigate the environmental suitability of the fleets under
 275 comparison, the LCA methodology (ISO, 2006a, 2006b) was applied first to each vehicle
 276 system and then to each fleet (once vehicles were arranged into fleets by means of the
 277 energy analysis results). Figure 4a shows the system boundaries considered for each
 278 vehicle, involving both the fuel life cycle and the vehicle one (Ricardo E&E, 2020). The
 279 former includes the (WTW) stages of production, distribution and use of the fuel,
 280 including one or two fuels depending on the type of vehicle (whether it uses a mixture or
 281 not). “Fuel 1” refers to CNG or gasoline, while “Fuel 2” stands for hydrogen. The vehicle
 282 life-cycle involves here the stages of vehicle manufacturing, operation and maintenance.
 283 Vehicle end-of-life was not included due to the acknowledged need for robust inventory
 284 data on this stage (Funazaki et al., 2003; Karagoz et al., 2020). The fuel and vehicle life
 285 cycles converge on the vehicle operation phase.

286 Figure 4b instead shows the system boundaries applied for a fleet system. Fleets
 287 were formed using different vehicles (in number and/or type). Inside a fleet, vehicles were
 288 homogeneously grouped by technology. In this regard, “Vehicle A” always refers to a
 289 type of vehicle that uses fossil fuel, pure or mixed with hydrogen, while “Vehicle B”
 290 (when present) always refers to FCEVs. The functional unit (FU) of the study was defined
 291 as 1 km travelled by each fleet.

292

293

294 **Figure 4:** System boundaries: (a) single vehicle, and (b) fleet.

295 The life-cycle environmental performance of each system was characterised in
296 terms of global warming impact potential (GWP), acidification impact potential (AP) and
297 cumulative non-renewable energy demand (CED) using the methods IPCC (2013), CML
298 (Guinée et al., 2001) and VDI (2012), respectively. The selection of these indicators was
299 based on their specific relevance to hydrogen energy systems (Valente et al., 2017a).

300 *2.4. Data acquisition*

301 Concerning fuels, harmonised life-cycle indicators based on previous studies were
302 used for hydrogen produced via WPE: carbon, acidification and non-renewable energy
303 footprints (Valente et al., 2019, 2018, 2017b) were adapted to the hydrogen pressure of
304 700 bar to comply with FCEV and H₂-Gasoline vehicle specifications (Candelaresi et al.,
305 2021a; Valente et al., 2020). Hydrogen distribution from the production site to the
306 refuelling point (100 km) by a tanker truck was considered (Sergeant et al., 2009).
307 Regarding CNG and gasoline production and distribution, background data from the
308ecoinvent database (Frischknecht et al., 2007) were used. Regarding hythane, it was
309 assumed that hydrogen is injected into the NG grid (blending) and distributed (100 km)
310 via pipeline to the refuelling point (Candelaresi et al., 2021a; Sergeant et al., 2009).

311 For most of the vehicle types involved in fleets composition, inventory data for
312 their manufacturing were directly retrieved from previous studies (Candelaresi et al.,
313 2021a; Valente et al., 2020). On the other hand, those vehicles not previously considered
314 are presented in Table 2. In particular, the inventories for the HEV Hythane and HEV H₂-
315 Gasoline options constitute a novelty of this work. The technical feasibility of these
316 options was not deemed a problem as they represent a combination of well-known
317 technologies: internal combustion engines with soft modifications to run with hydrogen

318 blends and common hybridisation by integration of an electrical propulsion system.

319 However, the willingness to invest in these two innovative vehicle technologies to put

320 them on the market will depend mainly on car manufacturers and policies.

321 **Table 2:** Main inventory data for vehicle production (values per one vehicle).

Item	Unit	HEV Hythane	HEV H ₂ -Gasoline	Gasoline	HEV Gasoline
Vehicle rated power	kW	80	80	80	80
Vehicle kerb weight	kg	1480	1425	1250	1400
Body and chassis	p	1	1	1	1
Fluids	p	1	1	1	1
ICE	kW	58.4	58.4	80	58.4
↳Steel, low-alloyed	kg	36.80	37.86	50.41	36.80
↳Aluminium	kg	30.22	31.28	41.40	30.22
↳Polyphenylene sulphide	kg	18.02	20.14	24.68	18.02
↳Lubricating oil	kg	6.37	6.37	8.73	6.37
Fuel system	p	1	1	1	1
↳Copper	kg	3.94	3.94	-	-
↳Polyvinylchloride	kg	0.92	0.92	-	-
↳Reinforcing steel	kg	-	1.45	1.45	1.45
Gasoline tank	p	-	1	1	1
↳High-density polyethylene, HDPE	kg	-	17.5	17.5	17.5
↳Injection moulding	kg	-	17.5	17.5	17.5
Tank CNG-II	kg	80	-	-	-
↳Steel, low-alloyed	kg	70	-	-	-
↳Epoxy resin, liquid	kg	6	-	-	-
↳Glass fibre	kg	4	-	-	-
Hydrogen tank (CNG-IV)	kg	-	18.60	-	-
↳Aluminium	kg	-	1.42	-	-
↳Carbon fibre	kg	-	3.96	-	-
↳Epoxy resin, liquid	kg	-	5.93	-	-
↳Glass fibre	kg	-	1.12	-	-
↳High-density polyethylene, HDPE	kg	-	2.05	-	-
↳Polyurethane, flexible foam	kg	-	0.93	-	-
↳Steel, low-alloyed	kg	-	2.13	-	-
↳Electricity	MJ	-	2.57	-	-
Exhaust system	p	1	1	1	1
↳Reinforcing steel	kg	34.9	34.9	34.9	34.9
↳Synthetic rubber	kg	1.45	1.45	1.45	1.45
↳Talc	kg	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4
↳Steel, low-alloyed	kg	25.2	25.2	25.2	25.2
↳Platinum	g	1.4	1.12	1.6	1.6
↳Palladium	g	0.7	0.42	0.6	0.6
↳Rhodium	g	0.64	0.48	0.3	0.3
↳Cerium concentrate	kg	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
↳Zirconium oxide	kg	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14
↳Aluminium oxide	kg	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02
↳Polyphenylene sulphide	kg	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Li-ion battery	kWh	1.8	1.8	-	1.8
Electric motor	kW	48.6	48.6	-	48.6
Power control unit	kg	33.3	33.3	-	33.3
Gearbox	kg	80	80	80	80
Start system	p	1	1	1	1
Cooling system ICE	kg	29.1	29.1	29.1	29.1
Electronics for control units	kg	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3
Tyres	p	4	4	4	4
Natural gas	MJ	1933	1933	1933	1933
Electricity	kWh	691	691	691	691

322 In addition, for the sake of completeness and traceability, the inventories for the
323 Gasoline and HEV Gasoline options are also presented. The procedure and sources for
324 the collection of the main inventory data for the stages of production, operation and
325 maintenance of individual vehicles have been extensively covered in Candelaresi et al.
326 (2021a) and are based on well-established life cycle databases such as ecoinvent
327 (Frischknecht et al., 2007) and GREET (Wang et al., 2007), industry specifications,
328 manufacturer statements, reports, and scientific literature.

329 For the options Gasoline and HEV Gasoline, data from technical datasheets
330 released by manufacturers, as well as from literature and databases, were retrieved. On
331 the other hand, for commercially unavailable vehicles (HEV Hythane and HEV H₂-
332 Gasoline), data collection was based on specific literature combined with technical
333 specifications regarding current HEVs. In particular, the ICE versions of Hythane and H₂-
334 Gasoline vehicles from Candelaresi et al. (2021a) were adapted to HEVs through the
335 different sizing of the thermal and electrical subsystems that make up the vehicle
336 powertrain. The overall rated power considered for individual HEVs is 80 kW (the same
337 as all the other vehicles), which –for the degree of hybridisation and the assumptions
338 made in Candelaresi et al. (2021a)– is obtained through a 58.4 kW ICE and a 48.6 kW
339 electric motor. In addition, HEVs present a 1.8 kWh Li-ion battery and a power control
340 unit for smart management of electrical flows. HEVs and ICE vehicles were considered
341 to involve the same glider, therefore the main differences in vehicle manufacturing are
342 linked to powertrain configurations (additional components such as tanks, batteries,
343 power control unit, etc.).

344 The HEV Hythane option is equipped with a 100-litre CNG-II tank (metal liner
345 hoop-wrapped with glass fibre and epoxy resin), in which about 15 kg of hythane can be
346 stored at 200 bar. It also involves a gaseous fuel distribution system and an exhaust gas
347 system in which the amounts of platinum group metals (PGMs) in the catalytic converter
348 are adjusted according to the emission characteristics of the vehicle.

349 Regarding the HEV H₂-Gasoline option, the differences in components (compared
350 to HEV Gasoline) are closely linked to the presence of hydrogen. Being a dual-fuel
351 vehicle, two separate tanks and fuel distribution systems are present on-board for each
352 fuel: gasoline is stored in a common plastic tank paired with a traditional fuel distribution
353 system, while pure hydrogen is stored in a composite cylinder at 700 bar (type-IV tank).
354 The 25-litre hydrogen tank (18.6 kg) can store about 1 kg H₂. The small amount of
355 hydrogen required by the vehicle mitigates hydrogen storage issues. Dedicated hydrogen
356 supply (refuel filler neck, valves, special pipes) and distribution (pressure reducer,
357 systems to prevent backfire, manifold/rail, gaskets, etc.) systems are also present, besides
358 minor ICE modifications such as hydrogen injectors (in addition to gasoline injectors)
359 and reinforced valve seats. Due to combustion improvements with respect to conventional
360 gasoline vehicles, a lower load of PGMs was considered in the catalytic converter. Further
361 details on the inventories of individual subsystems and components can be found in
362 Candelaresi et al. (2021a) and Valente et al. (2020).

363 Operational parameters regarding fuel consumption and tailpipe emissions are
364 those presented in Table 1. The values for the new vehicle concepts (HEV Hythane and
365 HEV H₂-Gasoline) were based on the H₂-blend vehicles in Candelaresi et al. (2021a),
366 adapted to vehicle hybridisation. These, in turn, were based on specific literature about

367 experimental tests and measures on ICEs according to the hydrogen percentage under
 368 examination for both NG (Genovese et al., 2011; Yan et al., 2017) and gasoline (Akif
 369 Ceviz et al., 2012; Conte and Boulouchos, 2008; Du et al., 2017, 2016; Shi et al., 2017)
 370 blends. The values considered for these two vehicle options correspond to a conservative
 371 approach and therefore present room for improvement through engine optimisation.

372 Values from Table 1 were used to derive the amounts of fuel consumption and
 373 tailpipe emissions throughout the entire vehicle life. Inventory data for vehicle operation
 374 and maintenance are presented in Table 3.

375 **Table 3:** Main inventory data for vehicle operation and maintenance (values per total kilometres travelled
 376 by one vehicle during its useful life).

Item	Unit	HEV Hythane	HEV H ₂ -Gasoline	Gasoline	HEV Gasoline	Ref. for inventory
Operational inputs						
Vehicle infrastructure	p	1	1	1	1	Table 2
Hydrogen fuel	t	0.187	0.176	-	-	a
Natural gas	GJ	284	-	-	-	b
Gasoline (unleaded)	t	-	6.14	11.25	7.43	b
Maintenance inputs						
Lubricating oil	kg	34.6	34.6	34.6	34.6	b, c
Ethylene glycol	kg	12.9	12.9	12.9	12.9	b, c
Decarbonised water	kg	8.58	8.58	8.58	8.58	b, c
Tyres	p	12	12	12	12	c, d
Li-ion battery	kWh	1.8	1.8	-	1.8	e, f
Emissions						
Carbon dioxide	t	17.2	18.6	31.6	22.5	Table 1
Carbon monoxide	kg	5.96	20.6	87.8	58.8	Table 1
Hydrocarbons, unspecified	kg	4.24	5.28	12.4	8.46	Table 1
Nitrogen oxides	kg	2.52	2.96	6.15	1.8	Table 1
Brake wear emissions	g	436	380	334	374	b
Road wear emissions	kg	4.79	4.19	3.67	4.11	b
Tyre wear emissions	kg	28.05	24.50	21.49	24.07	b
Kilometres travelled	km	320,000	300,000	300,000	300,000	g

a: Valente et al. (2020); b: Frischknecht et al. (2007); c: Wang et al. (2007); d: Bras and Cobert (2011);

e: Ellingsen et al. (2014); f: Majeau-Bettez et al. (2011); g: Candelaresi et al. (2021a)

377 The wear of tyres, brakes and road due to abrasion phenomena was taken into
 378 consideration, as it leads to emissions of particulate matter during the vehicle useful life.
 379 These emissions were calculated proportionally to each vehicle weight.

380 The life-cycle models presented in Tables 2 and 3 were implemented in SimaPro
381 9.4 using the ecoinvent database as the data source for background processes. The
382 environmental characterisation was carried out by taking into account the selected life-
383 cycle indicators and impact assessment methods. The combination of the LCA results for
384 the individual vehicles with the results of the energy analysis allows the evaluation of the
385 environmental performance of each fleet.

386 **3. Results and discussion**

387 *3.1. Energy analysis results*

388 Table 4 presents the energy analysis results for each of the fleet systems under
389 evaluation. According to the given energy input and vehicle fuel consumption, the annual
390 kilometres travelled by each vehicle type (i.e., homogeneously grouped by technology)
391 and the total annual kilometres travelled by each fleet were calculated. Additionally,
392 taking into account the passenger transport function of a fleet by means of an occupancy
393 rate of 1.6 for every vehicle (average number of passengers occupying a vehicle) (Archer
394 et al., 2018; EEA, 2016), the total annual passenger-km (pkm) associated with each fleet
395 were calculated.

396 Since the amount of energy entering the systems is the same, the fleets that exhibit
397 the highest number in terms of total km or pkm are those that achieve the best energy
398 performance. In this sense, Table 4 results show that the fleets that use blends outperform
399 those with separate use of the two fuels (e.g., F2 vs F1 or F4 vs F3), and that HEV fleets
400 behave better than those with simple ICEs (e.g., F3 vs F1, F4 vs F2 or F3 vs F2). The
401 same is true for fleets involving the use of gasoline, where a gradual improvement was
402 observed when switching from F5 to F8. This is due to an enhanced fuel economy of

403 vehicles that use blends with respect to the separate use of fuels, and of HEVs compared
404 to ICE vehicles. Thus, the fleets with the best performance were found to be F4 (involving
405 only HEV Hythane) and F8 (involving only HEV H₂-gasoline). As another finding, fleets
406 that involve the use of NG perform slightly better than their gasoline counterparts (e.g.,
407 F2 vs F6 or F3 vs F7). The worst strategies, among the analysed ones, would refer to the
408 simple combination of FCEVs and existing gasoline or CNG cars (F5 and F1). In this
409 sense, under specific circumstances hampering the use of hydrogen mixtures, HEVs
410 (instead of conventional cars) are recommended to be deployed along with FCEVs.

411 Table 5 presents the results in terms of the number of vehicles that make up each
412 fleet, penetration impact on the Italian fleet, and average fleet fuel economy, expressed
413 as fleet efficiency. Taking into account the total kilometres travelled by each vehicle type
414 and the fixed annual driving performance of each single vehicle (15,000 km), the number
415 of vehicles within each fleet was calculated. Considering the total number of passenger
416 cars circulating on Italian roads (presented in Section 2.2), national fleet penetration for
417 both the total number of vehicles in a fleet and only hydrogen-related vehicles were
418 estimated. Fleet average efficiency was calculated as the inverse of the weighted average
419 obtained by vehicle number in a fleet and vehicle specific energy consumption.

420 .

421 **Table 4:** Fleets' energy performance expressed as annual km travelled and annual passenger-km (pkm).

Fleet	Vehicles A [million km/year]	Vehicles B [million km/year]	Total km fleet [million km/year]	Vehicles A [million pkm/year]	Vehicles B [million pkm/year]	Total pkm fleet [million pkm/year]
F1: CNG + FCEV	4912.29	694.58	5606.87	7859.67	1111.33	8970.99
F2: Hythane	5957.68	-	5957.68	9532.29	-	9532.29
F3: HEV CNG + FCEV	7442.86	694.58	8137.45	11,908.58	1111.33	13,019.91
F4: HEV Hythane	9026.79	-	9026.79	14,442.86	-	14,442.86
F5: Gasoline + FCEV	4901.29	694.58	5595.88	7842.07	1111.33	8953.40
F6: H₂-Gasoline	5927.92	-	5927.92	9484.67	-	9484.67
F7: HEV Gasoline + FCEV	7426.20	694.58	8120.78	11,881.93	1111.33	12,993.25
F8: HEV H₂-Gasoline	8981.70	-	8981.70	14,370.72	-	14,370.72

422

423 **Table 5:** Number of vehicles, fleets composition and national fleet penetration.

Fleet	Number of Vehicles A [cars]	Number of Vehicles B [cars]	Total vehicle number in fleet [cars]	National fleet penetration [%]	Hydrogen-related vehicles national fleet penetration [%]	Fleet average efficiency [km/MJ]
F1: CNG + FCEV	327,486	46,305	373,791	0.941%	0.12%	0.648
F2: Hythane	397,178	-	397,178	1.000%	1.00%	0.689
F3: HEV CNG + FCEV	496,190	46,305	542,495	1.366%	0.12%	0.941
F4: HEV Hythane	601,785	-	601,785	1.515%	1.52%	1.044
F5: Gasoline + FCEV	326,752	46,305	373,057	0.939%	0.12%	0.647
F6: H₂-Gasoline	395,194	-	395,194	0.995%	0.99%	0.686
F7: HEV Gasoline + FCEV	495,080	46,305	541,385	1.363%	0.12%	0.939
F8: HEV H₂-Gasoline	598,779	-	598,779	1.508%	1.51%	1.039

424

425 Results in Table 5 are aligned with those in Table 4. In this case, the greater the
426 total number of vehicles that can be fuelled with the same energy input, the better the
427 energy performance of the fleet. The same observations made for Table 4 regarding the
428 fleets ranking are applicable. This trend is explained by the fleet average efficiency, with
429 the favourable effect of a large number of medium-efficient vehicles exceeding that of
430 high efficiency in a limited number of vehicles. The use of hydrogen-mixture vehicles
431 leads to homogeneous fleets with a relatively high average efficiency. Since HEVs enjoy
432 a more favourable fuel economy than their non-hybrid counterparts, the best performance
433 was found for the combined use of hydrogen mixtures and HEVs (F4 and F8).

434 The amount of hydrogen taken into consideration would power only 0.12% of the
435 national fleet if used in FCEVs. However, the same amount of hydrogen used in hythane
436 vehicles would result in a penetration of 1% of the national fleet, and 1.52% if the mixture
437 is used to fuel HEVs. This is due to the fact that each mixture-vehicle uses less hydrogen
438 than an FCEV, as well as to higher average fleet efficiency. According to the Italian
439 Automobile Club (ACI, 2021), the total number of CNG cars in circulation on Italian
440 roads in 2020 amounted to 978,832 vehicles. Having 5.28 kt of renewable hydrogen
441 annually available, it would be possible to convert 40.6% of the Italian CNG cars into
442 hythane cars or 61.5% into HEV hythane cars. Therefore, by moderately increasing the
443 assumed amount of renewable hydrogen available at the national level, the full Italian
444 CNG car fleet could move to the use of mixtures containing hydrogen.

445 In order to sensibly understand the suitability of the proposed strategies, an
446 environmental perspective is also needed. Contrary to the case in which hydrogen is used
447 in FCEVs, the use of the same amount of hydrogen in vehicles fuelled with a mixture

448 involves tailpipe exhaust emissions. Nevertheless, a fair environmental comparison
 449 between the fleets cannot be limited to tailpipe emissions, but a thorough LCA study is
 450 required. In this regard, for the subsequent LCA study, the results of the energy analysis
 451 were referred to one km travelled by each fleet (FU) and the fleets were represented as
 452 entities with a certain consumption of each of the fuels and a certain distance share
 453 associated with each type of vehicle (Table 6). As in Figure 4, “Fuel 1” refers to NG,
 454 hythane or gasoline depending on the fleet; “Fuel 2” corresponds to pure hydrogen;
 455 “Vehicle A” refers to a vehicle that uses fossil fuel, pure or mixed with hydrogen; and
 456 “Vehicle B” corresponds to an FCEV.

457 **Table 6:** Consumption of fuels per km travelled by each fleet and distance travelled with each vehicle type.

Fleet	Fuel 1 [g/FU]	Fuel 2 [mg/FU]	km Vehicles A [km/FU]	km Vehicles B [km/FU]
F1: CNG + FCEV	29.963 ^a	941.5 ^d	0.876	0.124
F2: Hythane	29.085 ^b	-	1	-
F3: HEV CNG + FCEV	20.645 ^a	648.7 ^d	0.915	0.085
F4: HEV Hythane	19.196 ^b	-	1	-
F5: Gasoline + FCEV	32.845 ^c	943.3 ^d	0.876	0.124
F6: H₂-Gasoline	31.006 ^c	890.5 ^d	1	-
F7: HEV Gasoline + FCEV	22.633 ^c	650.0 ^d	0.914	0.086
F8: HEV H₂-Gasoline	20.464 ^c	587.7 ^d	1	-

^a Amount of CNG required per each km travelled by the fleet.

^b Amount of hythane required per each km travelled by the fleet.

^c Amount of gasoline per each km travelled by the fleet.

^d Amount of hydrogen per each km travelled by the fleet.

458 3.2. Environmental results

459 Figure 5 shows the carbon footprint per km travelled by each fleet, including its
 460 breakdown according to the main life-cycle stages and the type of vehicle. In agreement
 461 with the energy analysis results in Section 3.1, the most favourable profile was found for
 462 the fleet of HEVs fuelled with hythane (F4).

463 For comparative purposes, in Figure 5 the results are also benchmarked against
464 two conventional fleets (B1 and B2) composed solely of either CNG or gasoline vehicles
465 under the same assumptions used to define the other fleets (total input energy of 8.65 PJ).
466 In this regard, the conventional CNG and gasoline fleets involve 353,373 and 352,582
467 cars, respectively. The comparison with conventional fleets allows evaluating the impact
468 reduction achieved when applying the proposed fleet strategies.

469 The carbon footprint reduction was found to range from 7% to 35% when
470 comparing either F1-F4 with the conventional CNG or F5-F8 with the conventional
471 gasoline fleet. The fleets showing an impact reduction >30% compared to their
472 conventional benchmark are F4 (HEV Hythane) and F8 (HEV H₂-Gasoline).

473 Regarding the carbon footprint breakdown, the emissions of the operational phase
474 (TTW) from type-A vehicles (which burn fossil fuel solely or in mixture) were found to
475 play the leading role, clearly ahead of vehicle manufacturing and fuel production.

476 Regarding FCEVs, while their fuel-use emissions are null, the role of vehicle
477 manufacturing becomes more relevant. It should be noted that, in this regard, the
478 infrastructure impact has to be read in light of the number of vehicles of each type.

479 The impact of renewable hydrogen, including production from WPE and
480 distribution, was found to be negligible compared to the total fleet impact. This is true
481 both in the case of pure hydrogen distributed via road (e.g., Vehicle B WTT in Figure 5)
482 and in the case of hydrogen distributed via pipeline and/or mixed with other fuels (a
483 fraction of Vehicle A WTT in Figure 5). Vehicle maintenance was also found to play a
484 minor role.

485

486

487 **Figure 5:** Breakdown of the carbon footprint of the proposed fleets per km travelled.

488 Concerning fuel production, it should be noted that the NG/gasoline used in type-
 489 A vehicles was considered entirely of fossil origin. Some regions, such as Italy, aim for
 490 an increased use of biomethane, especially that produced from urban, agricultural or
 491 livestock waste, encouraging its injection into the gas grid (GSE, 2021). If significant

492 amounts of biomethane were injected into the NG network, this could reduce the fuel-
493 related impact and methane-hydrogen blends would increase their renewable content.

494 As the purpose of this work is to help policy actors make well-supported decisions,
495 the total result deriving from each strategy was also considered. To that end, Figure 6
496 shows the total carbon footprint of the proposed fleet strategies. However, it should be
497 noted that each of the proposed fleets is composed of a different number of vehicles and
498 involves a different number of kilometres, therefore the total carbon footprint must be
499 interpreted accordingly. This means that some measures show a higher total carbon
500 footprint but lead to travel more kilometres (or, in other words, to power more vehicles),
501 whereas others show a lower impact but a poorer functional performance. Depending on
502 whether the policy-maker prioritises only the carbon footprint, only the energy
503 performance or both aspects, different fleet rankings are obtained. In the event that it is
504 decided to prioritise both the carbon footprint and the energy performance, the best fleets
505 would ideally be those with the lowest carbon footprint combined with the highest number
506 of kilometres travelled.

507

508 **Figure 6:** Total carbon footprint of the different fleet strategies proposed, and total
 509 distance travelled.

510 Besides the carbon footprint, the non-renewable energy footprint and the
 511 acidification impact per km travelled by each fleet were assessed. Figure 7 shows the
 512 breakdown by life-cycle stage and vehicle type for the CED and AP results of the
 513 proposed fleets, including their benchmarking against conventional fossil fleets.
 514 Regarding CED, the results show a strong correlation with the carbon footprint ones,
 515 leading to the same ranking of fleet strategies. It should be clarified that CED encloses
 516 the energy consumption cumulated over the life-cycle stages, whereas the energy analysis
 517 in Section 3.1 focuses on fuel consumption.

518 On the other hand, the AP results show different hotspots and ranking in
519 comparison with the previous results. From the breakdown in Figure 7, it can be observed
520 that vehicle manufacturing plays a key role in terms of acidification, which is linked to
521 the number and type of vehicles. Regarding single vehicles, the infrastructure
522 contribution to AP is relatively low for vehicles equipped with ICEs, intermediate for
523 HEVs, and very high for FCEVs (Candelaresi et al., 2021a). This trend is associated with
524 vehicle-specific aspects such as (i) electrification-related components such as batteries,
525 electric motors, power control units and fuel cell stacks, (ii) materials contained in the
526 above-mentioned components, such as platinum in fuel cells, and (iii) other vehicle
527 components such as heavier car gliders or hydrogen tanks involving composite material.
528 In HEVs and ICEs, especially CNG-fuelled ones, also the PGMs in the exhaust system
529 show a certain AP incidence. For these reasons, in terms of acidification, there is a change
530 in the ranking, with F2 performing slightly better than F4. The high contribution of
531 infrastructure to AP in FCEVs leads the fleets F1 and F3 to a higher acidification impact
532 than their CNG benchmark, while F2 and F4 remain slightly below the conventional CNG
533 fleet. Finally, gasoline-related fleets show a higher acidification footprint than those
534 related to NG, even though –apart from F5– they outperform their benchmark
535 (conventional gasoline fleet).

536

537 **Figure 7:** Breakdown of the energy and acidification footprints of the proposed fleets per

538 km travelled.

539 *3.3. Perspectives and final remarks*

540 Overall, the results show that the use of hydrogen blends would be beneficial
541 under different energy and environmental aspects to boost the hydrogen economy in the
542 short term. While this result could be affected by important changes in technical aspects
543 such as fuel consumption, lifespan, occupancy rate, weight and emission factors of each
544 vehicle, the key findings in this work are deemed robust as the technical parameters
545 considered in this paper are intended to give an average representation of each vehicle
546 technology. In this regard, Candelaresi et al. (2021b, 2021c) carried out a sensitivity
547 analysis to technical parameters, showing the functional dependencies of the LCA results
548 as the technical parameters vary. For instance, fuel consumption was found to have a
549 linear influence on the impact indicators. By considering a realistic range of variation
550 between worst and best cases of technical parameters, and its effect on LCA results, it
551 was possible to represent each average vehicle technology in a robust way. Finally, rather
552 than the numerical impact value of each vehicle or fleet, the key finding to be highlighted
553 refers to the possible relationship between the different fleet options and the strategic
554 opportunities that may arise from it.

555 Besides, other technical, economic and social co-benefits may derive from the use
556 of hydrogen blends. For instance, the increased use of hydrogen would result in a large
557 number of people acquainted with hydrogen energy systems, thereby favouring social
558 acceptance.

559 From a techno-economic point of view, the use of mixtures would allow the
560 immediate use of the available green hydrogen, relying on existing infrastructure and
561 vehicles with minor modifications and thus starting up a market without gaps in the

562 supply chain. In line with European goals, this would allow an initial concentration of
563 investments in the production of hydrogen from renewable or low-carbon sources. At a
564 later time, when green hydrogen production have already been scaled up, major
565 investments related to pure-hydrogen infrastructure and end uses could be attracted.
566 Alternatively, the hydrogen content in the mixture could be increased over time.

567 Among the opportunities derived from using blends, countries with a large number
568 of CNG refuelling points such as Italy could start up hydrogen deployment with minor
569 infrastructure modifications. Alternatively to hydrogen blending in pipeline, pure
570 renewable hydrogen could be transported (e.g., by road) from the production point and
571 used separately and/or mixed with CNG at the filling station. Regarding on-board storage,
572 methane can be stored at pressures similar to those already used for CNG (200 bar) and in
573 very similar tanks, already suitable or adapted for containing small amounts of hydrogen.
574 Storage pressure could be slightly raised to recover the loss of volumetric energy density
575 due to hydrogen addition or further extend the driving range. Similarly, the combustion
576 engine requires minimal modifications compared to a CNG engine.

577 As regards H₂-gasoline vehicles, in the absence of a dedicated hydrogen pipeline,
578 pure hydrogen should be transported to the refuelling station by road. Since the amount
579 of pure hydrogen stored in the vehicle is small, tank volume and weight issues associated
580 with pure hydrogen storage are mitigated. The ICE presents minor modifications with
581 respect to the conventional one, and the driving range is similar to that of a conventional
582 gasoline vehicle. A more distributed use of pure hydrogen would allow the creation of
583 several hydrogen refuelling stations of small size, which could be expanded at a later time
584 to allow also refuelling FCEVs. The increased number of users would allow these stations

585 to be exploited with high utilisation factors, thus accelerating the return on investment.
586 Furthermore, the increased number of small filling stations would enable an enhanced
587 coverage of the national road network, hastening action on the main transport arteries and
588 points of national/European strategic interest such as big cities, main highways and the
589 Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T) core.

590 **4. Conclusions**

591 This study explored –from an energy and life-cycle environmental perspective–
592 eight innovative fleet strategies for the short-term implementation of hydrogen in road
593 transport (passenger cars) at the national level. The proposed strategies achieve a carbon
594 footprint reduction ranging between 7% and 35% with respect to their conventional fleet
595 benchmark. It is concluded that strategies using hydrogen mixtures in homogeneous fleets
596 are more suitable than those separately using hydrogen and fossil fuels in heterogeneous
597 fleets. In particular, strategies based on blends of natural gas and hydrogen (hythane)
598 generally outperform those based on gasoline-hydrogen mixtures. Moreover, fleets
599 involving hybrid electric vehicles perform better than those involving internal combustion
600 engines. Thus, the best results were generally found for the fleet strategy based on the use
601 of hythane in hybrid electric vehicles (35% reduction in carbon footprint with respect to
602 its benchmark). Where this is not possible or under policy scenarios prioritising the
603 separate use of hydrogen, it is advisable to encourage fleets involving both hybrid and
604 fuel cell electric vehicles. The fleet strategies involving the use of hydrogen mixture and
605 internal combustion engines could arise as a first step towards their hybrid versions as
606 they would be preferred over those involving traditional vehicles alongside fuel cell
607 electric vehicles. Overall, also taking into account potential technical, economic and

608 social advantages, the use of hydrogen blends could facilitate the transition towards an
609 environmentally sustainable transport while hastening the advent of the hydrogen
610 economy.

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